

Fractional Newton-type inequalities by using Bounded and Lipschitzian functions

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Abstract

In the present article, we establish some Newton-type inequalities for bounded functions by Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals. In addition, we construct some Riemann-Liouville fractional Newton-type inequalities for Lipschitzian functions.

1. Introduction

Many The inequality theory is a famous subject in many mathematical areas and remains an interesting research field with a great deal applications. In addition, convex functions have also a significant place in the theory of inequality. Furthermore, fractional calculus has been the focus of attraction for mathematicians in mathematical sciences because of its fundamental properties and applications in real-life problems. In consequence of the importance of fractional calculus, mathematicians have studied several fractional integral inequalities. It can be proved the bounds of new inequalities by using not only Hermite-Hadamard type inequalities but also and Simpson, Newton, and Euler-Maclaurin-type inequalities.

Let us consider $f \in L_1[a, b]$. The Riemann-Liouville integrals $J_{a+}^\alpha f$ and $J_{b-}^\alpha f$ of order $\alpha > 0$ with $a \geq 0$ are defined by

$$J_{a+}^\alpha f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_a^x (x-t)^{\alpha-1} f(t) dt, \quad x > a$$

and

$$J_{b-}^\alpha f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_x^b (t-x)^{\alpha-1} f(t) dt, \quad x < b,$$

respectively [7, 13]. Here, $\Gamma(\alpha)$ denotes the Gamma function and its described as

$$\Gamma(\alpha) = \int_0^\infty e^{-u} u^{\alpha-1} du.$$

The fractional integral reduces to the classical integral for the case of $\alpha = 1$.

Simpson's inequalities have the following Simpson's rules:

- Simpson's quadrature formula (Simpson's 1/3 rule) is formulated as follows:

$$\int_a^b f(x) dx \approx \frac{b-a}{6} \left[f(a) + 4f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + f(b) \right]. \quad (1)$$

- Simpson's second formula or Newton-Cotes quadrature formula (Simpson's 3/8 rule (cf. [3])) is formulated as follows:

$$\int_a^b f(x) dx \approx \frac{b-a}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right].$$

Formulae (1) and (2) hold for every function f with continuous 4th derivative on $[a, b]$.

The most popular Newton-Cotes quadrature containing three-point Simpson type inequality is as follows:

Theorem 1 Let $f: [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ denote a four times differentiable and continuous function on (a, b) , and let $\|f^{(4)}\|_\infty = \sup_{x \in (a,b)} |f^{(4)}(x)| < \infty$. Then, the following inequality holds:

$$\left| \frac{1}{6} \left[f(a) + 4f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(x) dx \right| \leq \frac{1}{2880} \|f^{(4)}\|_\infty (b-a)^4.$$

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Dragomir [4] proved an estimation of remainder for Simpson's quadrature formula for the case of bounded variation functions and applications in theory of special means. Moreover, some fractional Simpson type inequalities for the case of function whose second derivatives in absolute value are convex given in [8]. Budak et al. [1] established some variants of Simpson type inequalities for the case of differentiable convex functions by generalized fractional integrals. For further information concerned Simpson type inequalities and some properties of Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals, the reader is referred to [2, 12] and the references therein.

Classical closed type quadrature rules is the Simpson 3/8 rule based on the Simpson 3/8 inequality as follows:

Theorem 2 Let $f: [a, b] \rightarrow R$ denote a four times differentiable and continuous function on (a, b) , and let $\|f^{(4)}\|_{\infty} = \sup_{x \in (a,b)} |f^{(4)}(x)| < \infty$. Then, one has the inequality

$$\left| \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(x) dx \right| \leq \frac{1}{6480} \|f^{(4)}\|_{\infty} (b-a)^4.$$

Simpson's second rule has the rule of three-point Newton-Cotes quadrature, hence evaluations for three steps quadratic kernel are sometimes called Newton type results in the literature. Newton type inequalities have been investigated by many researchers extensively. For instance, Erden et al. [5] proved some new integral inequalities of Newton type for the case of functions whose first derivative in absolute value at certain power are arithmetically-harmonically convex. By using the Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals, several Newton type inequalities for the case of differentiable convex functions were proved and some fractional Newton type inequalities for the case of bounded variation functions were presented in [9]. Moreover, Gao and Shi [6] proved new Newton type inequalities based on convexity and some applications for special cases of real functions are also established. Furthermore, Sitthiwiratham et al. [15] presented some Newton type inequalities by using Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals and several fractional Newton type inequalities for the case of bounded variation functions were given. For the case of further informations concerned with Newton type of inequalities including convex differentiable functions, it can be referred to [10, 11, 14] and the references therein.

Lemma 1 If $f: [a, b] \rightarrow R$ is an absolutely continuous on (a, b) such that $f' \in L_1([a, b])$, then the following equality

$$\frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] \tag{3}$$

$$- \frac{\Gamma(\alpha+1)}{2(b-a)^\alpha} [J_{a^+}^\alpha f(b) + J_{b^-}^\alpha f(a)] = \frac{(b-a)}{2} [I_1 + I_2 + I_3],$$

where

$$\begin{cases} I_1 = \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left(t^\alpha - \frac{1}{8}\right) [f'(tb + (1-t)a) - f'(ta + (1-t)b)] dt, \\ I_2 = \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left(t^\alpha - \frac{1}{2}\right) [f'(tb + (1-t)a) - f'(ta + (1-t)b)] dt, \\ I_3 = \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left(t^\alpha - \frac{7}{8}\right) [f'(tb + (1-t)a) - f'(ta + (1-t)b)] dt. \end{cases}$$

2. Bounded functions: Newton-type inequalities with fractional integrals

In this section, we deal with some Euler-Maclaurin-type inequalities for bounded functions via fractional integrals.

Theorem 3 Note that the conditions of Lemma 1 hold. If there exist $m, M \in R$ such that $m \leq f'(t) \leq M$ for $t \in [a, b]$, then it follows

$$\left| \frac{1}{8} \left[3f\left(\frac{5a+b}{6}\right) + 2f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+5b}{6}\right) \right] - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha+1)}{2(b-a)^\alpha} [J_{a^+}^\alpha f(b) + J_{b^-}^\alpha f(a)] \right| \leq \frac{b-a}{2} \{\Omega_1(\alpha) + \Omega_2(\alpha) + \Omega_3(\alpha)\} (M-m).$$

Here,

$$\begin{aligned} \Omega_1(\alpha) &= \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| t^\alpha - \frac{1}{8} \right| dt \\ &= \begin{cases} \frac{2\alpha}{1+\alpha} \left(\frac{1}{8}\right)^{1+\frac{1}{\alpha}} + \frac{1}{3^{\alpha+1}(\alpha+1)} - \frac{1}{24}, & 0 < \alpha \leq \frac{\ln\left(\frac{1}{8}\right)}{\ln\left(\frac{1}{3}\right)}, \\ \frac{1}{24} - \frac{1}{3^{\alpha+1}(\alpha+1)}, & \alpha > \frac{\ln\left(\frac{1}{8}\right)}{\ln\left(\frac{1}{3}\right)}, \end{cases} \\ \Omega_2(\alpha) &= \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| t^\alpha - \frac{1}{2} \right| dt \end{aligned}$$

$$= \begin{cases} \frac{2^{1+\alpha} - 1}{3^{\alpha+1}(\alpha + 1)} - \frac{1}{6}, & 0 < \alpha \leq \frac{\ln(\frac{1}{2})}{\ln(\frac{1}{3})}, \\ \frac{\alpha}{1 + \alpha} \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^{\frac{1}{\alpha}} + \frac{1 + 2^{1+\alpha}}{3^{\alpha+1}(\alpha + 1)} - \frac{1}{2}, & \frac{\ln(\frac{1}{2})}{\ln(\frac{1}{3})} < \alpha \leq \frac{\ln(\frac{1}{2})}{\ln(\frac{2}{3})}, \\ \frac{1}{6} - \frac{2^{1+\alpha} - 1}{3^{\alpha+1}(\alpha + 1)}, & \alpha > \frac{\ln(\frac{1}{2})}{\ln(\frac{2}{3})}, \end{cases}$$

and

$$\Omega_3(\alpha) = \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| t^\alpha - \frac{7}{8} \right| dt$$

$$= \begin{cases} \frac{3^{1+\alpha} - 2^{1+\alpha}}{3^{\alpha+1}(\alpha + 1)} - \frac{7}{24}, & 0 < \alpha \leq \frac{\ln(\frac{7}{8})}{\ln(\frac{2}{3})}, \\ \frac{2\alpha}{1 + \alpha} \left(\frac{7}{8}\right)^{\frac{1}{\alpha}} + \frac{2^{1+\alpha} + 3^{1+\alpha}}{3^{\alpha+1}(\alpha + 1)} - \frac{35}{24}, & \alpha > \frac{\ln(\frac{7}{8})}{\ln(\frac{2}{3})}. \end{cases}$$

Proof. By using the Lemma 1, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] \\ & - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha + 1)}{2(b-a)^\alpha} [J_{a^+}^\alpha f(b) + J_{b^-}^\alpha f(a)] \\ & = \frac{b-a}{2} \left\{ \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left(t^\alpha - \frac{1}{8} \right) \left[f'(tb + (1-t)a) - \frac{m+M}{2} \right] dt \right. \\ & + \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left(t^\alpha - \frac{1}{8} \right) \left[\frac{m+M}{2} - f'(ta + (1-t)b) \right] dt \\ & + \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left(t^\alpha - \frac{1}{2} \right) \left[f'(tb + (1-t)a) - \frac{m+M}{2} \right] dt \\ & + \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left(t^\alpha - \frac{1}{2} \right) \left[\frac{m+M}{2} - f'(ta + (1-t)b) \right] dt \\ & + \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left(t^\alpha - \frac{7}{8} \right) \left[f'(tb + (1-t)a) - \frac{m+M}{2} \right] dt \\ & \left. + \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left(t^\alpha - \frac{7}{8} \right) \left[\frac{m+M}{2} - f'(ta + (1-t)b) \right] dt \right\}. \end{aligned}$$

Through the absolute value of (5), we get

$$\left| \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha + 1)}{2(b-a)^\alpha} [J_{a^+}^\alpha f(b) + J_{b^-}^\alpha f(a)] \right|$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \leq \frac{b-a}{2} \left\{ \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| t^\alpha - \frac{1}{8} \right| \left| f'(tb + (1-t)a) - \frac{m+M}{2} \right| dt \right. \\ & + \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| t^\alpha - \frac{1}{8} \right| \left| \frac{m+M}{2} - f'(ta + (1-t)b) \right| dt \\ & + \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| t^\alpha - \frac{1}{2} \right| \left| f'(tb + (1-t)a) - \frac{m+M}{2} \right| dt \\ & + \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| t^\alpha - \frac{1}{2} \right| \left| \frac{m+M}{2} - f'(ta + (1-t)b) \right| dt \\ & + \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| t^\alpha - \frac{7}{8} \right| \left| f'(tb + (1-t)a) - \frac{m+M}{2} \right| dt \\ & \left. + \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| t^\alpha - \frac{7}{8} \right| \left| \frac{m+M}{2} - f'(ta + (1-t)b) \right| dt \right\}. \end{aligned}$$

It is known that $m \leq f'(t) \leq M$ for $t \in [a, b]$. Then, we have

$$\left| f'(tb + (1-t)a) - \frac{m+M}{2} \right| \leq \frac{M-m}{2}, \quad (6)$$

$$\left| \frac{m+M}{2} - f'(ta + (1-t)b) \right| \leq \frac{M-m}{2}. \quad (7)$$

With the help of the (6) and (7), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha + 1)}{2(b-a)^\alpha} [J_{a^+}^\alpha f(b) + J_{b^-}^\alpha f(a)] \right| \\ & \leq \frac{b-a}{2} (M-m) \\ & \times \left\{ \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| t^\alpha - \frac{1}{8} \right| dt + \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| t^\alpha - \frac{1}{2} \right| dt + \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| t^\alpha - \frac{7}{8} \right| dt \right\} \\ & = \frac{b-a}{2} \{ \Omega_1(\alpha) + \Omega_2(\alpha) + \Omega_3(\alpha) \} (M-m). \end{aligned}$$

Corollary 1 If we select $\alpha = 1$ in Theorem 3, then we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(t) dt \right| \\ & \leq \frac{25(b-a)}{576} (M-m). \end{aligned}$$

Corollary 2 Under assumption of Theorem 3, if there exist $M \in R^+$ such that $|f'(t)| \leq M$ for all $t \in [a, b]$, then we have

$$\left| \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha + 1)}{2(b-a)^\alpha} [J_{a^+}^\alpha f(b) + J_{b^-}^\alpha f(a)] \right|$$

$$\leq \frac{b-a}{2} \{\Omega_1(\alpha) + \Omega_2(\alpha) + \Omega_3(\alpha)\}M.$$

and

$$\Omega_6(\alpha) = \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 t \left| t^\alpha - \frac{7}{8} \right| dt$$

Corollary 3 Let us consider $\alpha = 1$ in Corollary 2. Then, the following inequality holds:

$$\left| \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(t) dt \right| \leq \frac{25(b-a)}{288} M.$$

3. Lipschitzian functions: Fractional Newton-type inequalities

In this section, we give some fractional Euler-Maclaurin-type inequalities for Lipschitzian functions.

Theorem 4 Assume that the assumptions of Lemma 1 are valid. If f' is a L -Lipschitzian function on $[a, b]$, then the following inequality holds:

$$\left| \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha+1)}{2(b-a)^\alpha} [J_{a^+}^\alpha f(b) + J_{b^-}^\alpha f(a)] \right| \leq \frac{(b-a)^2}{2} L \times \{2\Omega_4(\alpha) - \Omega_1(\alpha) + 2\Omega_5(\alpha) - \Omega_2(\alpha) + 2\Omega_6(\alpha) - \Omega_3(\alpha)\}.$$

Here,

$$\Omega_4(\alpha) = \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} t \left| t^\alpha - \frac{1}{8} \right| dt$$

$$= \begin{cases} \frac{\alpha}{2+\alpha} \left(\frac{1}{8}\right)^{1+\frac{2}{\alpha}} + \frac{1}{3^{\alpha+2}(\alpha+2)} - \frac{1}{144}, & 0 < \alpha \leq \frac{\ln(\frac{1}{8})}{\ln(\frac{1}{3})}, \\ \frac{1}{144} - \frac{1}{3^{\alpha+2}(\alpha+2)}, & \alpha > \frac{\ln(\frac{1}{8})}{\ln(\frac{1}{3})}, \end{cases}$$

$$\Omega_5(\alpha) = \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} t \left| t^\alpha - \frac{1}{2} \right| dt$$

$$= \begin{cases} \frac{2^{2+\alpha}-1}{3^{\alpha+2}(\alpha+2)} - \frac{1}{12}, & 0 < \alpha \leq \frac{\ln(\frac{1}{2})}{\ln(\frac{1}{3})}, \\ \frac{\alpha}{2+\alpha} \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^{1+\frac{2}{\alpha}} + \frac{1+2^{2+\alpha}}{3^{\alpha+2}(\alpha+2)} - \frac{5}{36}, & \frac{\ln(\frac{1}{2})}{\ln(\frac{1}{3})} < \alpha \leq \frac{\ln(\frac{1}{2})}{\ln(\frac{2}{3})}, \\ \frac{1}{12} - \frac{2^{2+\alpha}-1}{3^{\alpha+2}(\alpha+2)}, & \alpha > \frac{\ln(\frac{1}{2})}{\ln(\frac{2}{3})}, \end{cases}$$

$$= \begin{cases} \frac{3^{2+\alpha} - 2^{2+\alpha}}{3^{\alpha+2}(\alpha+2)} - \frac{35}{144}, & 0 < \alpha \leq \frac{\ln(\frac{7}{8})}{\ln(\frac{2}{3})}, \\ \frac{\alpha}{2+\alpha} \left(\frac{7}{8}\right)^{1+\frac{2}{\alpha}} + \frac{2^{2+\alpha} + 3^{2+\alpha}}{3^{\alpha+2}(\alpha+2)} - \frac{91}{144}, & \alpha > \frac{\ln(\frac{7}{8})}{\ln(\frac{2}{3})}. \end{cases}$$

Proof. With the aid of Lemma 1 and since f' is L -Lipschitzian function, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha+1)}{2(b-a)^\alpha} [J_{a^+}^\alpha f(b) + J_{b^-}^\alpha f(a)] \right| \\ &= \left| \frac{b-a}{2} \left\{ \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left(t^\alpha - \frac{1}{8}\right) [f'(tb + (1-t)a) - f'(ta + (1-t)b)] dt \right. \right. \\ & \quad + \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left(t^\alpha - \frac{1}{2}\right) [f'(tb + (1-t)a) - f'(ta + (1-t)b)] dt \\ & \quad \left. \left. + \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left(t^\alpha - \frac{7}{8}\right) [f'(tb + (1-t)a) - f'(ta + (1-t)b)] dt \right\} \right| \\ &\leq \frac{b-a}{2} \left\{ \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| t^\alpha - \frac{1}{8} \right| |f'(tb + (1-t)a) - f'(ta + (1-t)b)| dt \right. \\ & \quad + \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| t^\alpha - \frac{1}{2} \right| |f'(tb + (1-t)a) - f'(ta + (1-t)b)| dt \\ & \quad \left. + \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| t^\alpha - \frac{7}{8} \right| |f'(tb + (1-t)a) - f'(ta + (1-t)b)| dt \right\} \\ &\leq \frac{b-a}{2} \left\{ \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| t^\alpha - \frac{1}{8} \right| L(2t-1)(b-a) dt \right. \\ & \quad \left. + \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| t^\alpha - \frac{1}{2} \right| L(2t-1)(b-a) dt \right. \\ & \quad \left. + \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| t^\alpha - \frac{7}{8} \right| L(2t-1)(b-a) dt \right\} = \frac{(b-a)^2}{2} L \\ & \times \{2\Omega_4(\alpha) - \Omega_1(\alpha) + 2\Omega_5(\alpha) - \Omega_2(\alpha) + 2\Omega_6(\alpha) - \Omega_3(\alpha)\}. \end{aligned}$$

Corollary 4 Consider $\alpha = 1$ in Theorem 4. Then, the following Euler-Maclaurin-type inequality holds:

$$\left| \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(t) dt \right| \leq \frac{475(b-a)^2}{20736} L.$$

4. Lipschitzian functions: Fractional Newton-type inequalities

In this section, we give some fractional Euler-Maclaurin-type inequalities for Lipschitzian functions.

Theorem 4 Assume that the assumptions of Lemma 1 are valid. If f' is a L -Lipschitzian function on $[a, b]$, then the following inequality holds:

$$\left| \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha+1)}{2(b-a)^\alpha} [J_{a^+}^\alpha f(b) + J_{b^-}^\alpha f(a)] \right| \leq \frac{(b-a)^2}{2} L \times \{2\Omega_4(\alpha) - \Omega_1(\alpha) + 2\Omega_5(\alpha) - \Omega_2(\alpha) + 2\Omega_6(\alpha) - \Omega_3(\alpha)\}.$$

Here,

$$\Omega_4(\alpha) = \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} t \left| t^\alpha - \frac{1}{8} \right| dt = \begin{cases} \frac{\alpha}{2+\alpha} \left(\frac{1}{8}\right)^{1+\frac{2}{\alpha}} + \frac{1}{3^{\alpha+2}(\alpha+2)} - \frac{1}{144}, & 0 < \alpha \leq \frac{\ln(\frac{1}{8})}{\ln(\frac{1}{3})}, \\ \frac{1}{144} - \frac{1}{3^{\alpha+2}(\alpha+2)}, & \alpha > \frac{\ln(\frac{1}{8})}{\ln(\frac{1}{3})}, \end{cases}$$

$$\Omega_5(\alpha) = \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} t \left| t^\alpha - \frac{1}{2} \right| dt = \begin{cases} \frac{2^{2+\alpha}-1}{3^{\alpha+2}(\alpha+2)} - \frac{1}{12}, & 0 < \alpha \leq \frac{\ln(\frac{1}{2})}{\ln(\frac{1}{3})}, \\ \frac{\alpha}{2+\alpha} \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^{1+\frac{2}{\alpha}} + \frac{1+2^{2+\alpha}}{3^{\alpha+2}(\alpha+2)} - \frac{5}{36}, & \frac{\ln(\frac{1}{2})}{\ln(\frac{1}{3})} < \alpha \leq \frac{\ln(\frac{1}{2})}{\ln(\frac{2}{3})}, \\ \frac{1}{12} - \frac{2^{2+\alpha}-1}{3^{\alpha+2}(\alpha+2)}, & \alpha > \frac{\ln(\frac{1}{2})}{\ln(\frac{2}{3})}, \end{cases}$$

and

$$\Omega_6(\alpha) = \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 t \left| t^\alpha - \frac{7}{8} \right| dt = \begin{cases} \frac{3^{2+\alpha}-2^{2+\alpha}}{3^{\alpha+2}(\alpha+2)} - \frac{35}{144}, & 0 < \alpha \leq \frac{\ln(\frac{7}{8})}{\ln(\frac{2}{3})}, \\ \frac{\alpha}{2+\alpha} \left(\frac{7}{8}\right)^{1+\frac{2}{\alpha}} + \frac{2^{2+\alpha}+3^{2+\alpha}}{3^{\alpha+2}(\alpha+2)} - \frac{91}{144}, & \alpha > \frac{\ln(\frac{7}{8})}{\ln(\frac{2}{3})}. \end{cases}$$

Proof. With the aid of Lemma 1 and since f' is L -Lipschitzian function, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha+1)}{2(b-a)^\alpha} [J_{a^+}^\alpha f(b) + J_{b^-}^\alpha f(a)] \right| \\ &= \left| \frac{b-a}{2} \left\{ \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left(t^\alpha - \frac{1}{8}\right) [f'(tb + (1-t)a) - f'(ta + (1-t)b)] dt \right. \right. \\ & \quad + \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left(t^\alpha - \frac{1}{2}\right) [f'(tb + (1-t)a) - f'(ta + (1-t)b)] dt \\ & \quad \left. \left. + \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left(t^\alpha - \frac{7}{8}\right) [f'(tb + (1-t)a) - f'(ta + (1-t)b)] dt \right\} \right| \\ & \leq \frac{b-a}{2} \left\{ \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| t^\alpha - \frac{1}{8} \right| |f'(tb + (1-t)a) - f'(ta + (1-t)b)| dt \right. \\ & \quad + \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| t^\alpha - \frac{1}{2} \right| |f'(tb + (1-t)a) - f'(ta + (1-t)b)| dt \\ & \quad \left. + \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| t^\alpha - \frac{7}{8} \right| |f'(tb + (1-t)a) - f'(ta + (1-t)b)| dt \right\} \\ & \leq \frac{b-a}{2} \left\{ \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| t^\alpha - \frac{1}{8} \right| L(2t-1)(b-a) dt \right. \\ & \quad + \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| t^\alpha - \frac{1}{2} \right| L(2t-1)(b-a) dt \\ & \quad \left. + \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| t^\alpha - \frac{7}{8} \right| L(2t-1)(b-a) dt \right\} = \frac{(b-a)^2}{2} L \times \{2\Omega_4(\alpha) - \Omega_1(\alpha) + 2\Omega_5(\alpha) - \Omega_2(\alpha) + 2\Omega_6(\alpha) - \Omega_3(\alpha)\}. \end{aligned}$$

Corollary 4 Consider $\alpha = 1$ in Theorem 4. Then, the following Euler-Maclaurin-type inequality holds:

$$\left| \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(t) dt \right| \leq \frac{475(b-a)^2}{20736} L.$$

5. Conclusions

Some Euler-Maclaurin-type inequalities are presented for the case of differentiable convex functions by using Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals. In addition, we give an example using graphs in order to indicate that our main result is correct. Our results can be extended by mathematicians in future studies by applying different variations of convex function classes.

Declaration of Ethical Standards

The authors of this article declare that the materials and methods used in this study do not require ethical committee permission and legal-special permission.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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